

An evaluation of the state-of-the-art testing algorithms for Android mobile applications

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1. Introduction

In the past two decades, the mobile phone industry has grown into one of the largest markets in the world. In 2021, over 7 billion people owned smartphones[30]. There are over 3 million[31] mobile applications developed to be used on these phones, and the average consumer uses over 40 different applications every month[32]. The smartphone has overtaken the computer as the platform of choice for personal computing. People use it for entertainment, banking, networking, map-reading, gaming, and much more. With software so widespread, it is critical that there are methods and tools to test for bugs, errors, and security vulnerabilities.

As smartphone technology and apps get deeply integrated into every aspect of our lives, they must be secure and privacy-aware. Cybersecurity and safety are top concerns for government, companies, and individuals. Secondly, an app's stability is a key driver of user engagement with the app. Undiscovered bugs and errors are not only potential security vulnerabilities waiting for exploitation, but they also lead to poor user experience. On the other hand, app development is a democratized industry, and most apps are developed by individuals or small companies. These developers do not have the resources or expertise to test the apps for all scenarios, specifically security and privacy vulnerabilities. Hackers are innovative and security threats are constantly evolving, making it hard to keep at the cutting edge of security. Lastly, as apps offer richer interactions, there is an explosion of complex events and states that an app needs to be tested for. Thus, manual testing cannot provide the rigor needed to make these apps secure, and automated testing is required.

There are currently several approaches and tools to automate testing for mobile apps with varying levels of performance along the dimensions of code coverage, fault test detection, test execution time, and ease of use. These tools use a variety of methods to automate testing, ranging from sending random inputs to machine learning. The majority of research in the automated testing field has been directed toward the Android platform. Android has the largest share of the current mobile market and is open-source in nature, making it an appealing target for research[29]. Furthermore, a stunning 98% of mobile malware targets the Android platform[33], so it is critical that we can rapidly detect and eliminate security vulnerabilities.

Figure I: Market share of mobile operating systems

In this paper, we review the current state-of-the-art methods for automated Android testing and evaluate their unique approaches, strengths, and limitations. We establish a framework for comparing these approaches based on code coverage, error detection, and test execution time as the key factors of consideration. Then we present a comparison of the 6 widely used tools built on these methodologies and evaluate them for their effectiveness. Lastly, we present the limitations of the current state-of-the-art methods and outline ideas for future work in this area.

2. Literature Review: Approaches to Automated Testing

The space of automated testing algorithms and tools is evolving rapidly as the problem of efficiently testing mobile apps impacts more software developers and companies. The majority of the research is directed towards the Android platform, as it is an open-source platform and has the largest share of mobile platforms. Approaches for automated Android black-box test case generation and test execution can be broadly classified into four categories: random testing, model-based testing, search-based testing, and machine learning-based testing. In this section, we will review the state-of-the-art techniques and tools for each of these categories. Before we discuss the testing methods, let us establish common terms to describe apps and their characteristics.

An application is composed of many widgets or screens that a user interacts with. The widgets are organized in a tree-like structure, called a GUI tree in this paper[4-7]. An activity or event can be a button, a text box, or a container with a layout. It can support various GUI events such as clicking and swiping. A widget has four categories of attributes describing its type (e.g., class), appearance (e.g. text), functionalities (e.g., clickable and scrollable), and the designated order among sibling widgets (i.e., index)[7]. As apps become more complex, they use more complex interactions and actions (text, scrolling, swiping, double clicks, etc.), resulting in a combinatorial explosion in the number of scenarios that the testing tool needs to cover.

2.1 Random testing

In the Random testing approach, apps are tested by generating random, independent inputs[1] to simulate user interaction with the app and test multiple code paths with no assumptions about how the app is implemented. Figure 1.1 illustrates the typical workflow for random testing methods.

Figure 1.1: Random testing workflow

Monkey[2] is one of the most popular random testing frameworks for Android apps. It generates and sends pseudo-random inputs of user and system events to the app under test and has helped discover many bugs. The advantage of a random testing approach is that it can test the app's robustness for arbitrary sequences of inputs. The method lends itself to fully automated and black-box testing as it does not require app specific information to design tests and user inputs. There are some disadvantages as well. Random testing methods are prone to longer test execution times as the random nature of the inputs prevents prioritizing testing of common user paths. This can result in significant time spent on uncommon user workflows. Second, the random nature of test execution also makes it harder to reproduce crashes and failures. Finally, there is no way to use or learn the interactions and transitions of app widgets for optimizing test cases based on previous tests. It is a brute force approach and can have high variance in coverage and test sequence length across apps.

2.2 Model-based testing

A model-based testing tool aims to explore the app[7] to discover new widgets and create a model and state machine for the app's GUI. It then systematically exploits the models to exercise interactions among the discovered widgets. The tool interacts iteratively with the app under test. Initially, the testing tool starts with an empty state machine as the model. During each iteration, the testing tool obtains the current widget tree of the app, assesses if this widget maps to an existing state or a new state, and determines the next GUI action to interact with the app. By repeating this process, it builds a model of app states and

GUI actions to reach those states.

Figure 1.2: Model-based testing workflow

GUI Model: A GUI model is a graph of nodes that are typically rooted at the home screen of the app, with each node representing a unique screen or GUI widget in the app. The node path refers to the ordered sequence of events (clicks, swipes, etc.) that will take a user from the home screen to that node. Each node has a set of attributes and a set of actions associated with it.

State Extraction: State Extraction refers to the procedure of reading the GUI attributes and actions from the app and identifies whether we have encountered a new widget or if the widget can be mapped back to an existing state and model action. In general, state extraction is realized based on the similarity of node paths of GUI actions [4], [5], [8]. Specifically, state extraction determines two GUI states as equivalent if (1) they have the same action type and (2) their full node paths can be reduced to the same path by removing irrelevant attributes. A black box testing tool uses heuristics-based rules to apply different reductions to different widgets to achieve a proper abstraction granularity. This step of state extraction and reduction is key to model-based testing methods. It is an active area of research as it involves trade-offs between model size and model precision.

Event Selection: Event selection refers to the decision tree that an automated testing tool chooses to explore the app under test. There are several factors that influence exploration strategy e.g. locality of the code execution, prioritizing new paths first (greedy) over traversed paths. The decision algorithm can make a significant difference in the tool's capability to balance between coverage of the app and the execution time.

Model-based testing offers multiple significant advantages over pure random testing. One of its biggest benefits lies in its ability to leverage information it gains during prior testing to refine the model. This information can also be used to avoid repeating events at a previously visited screen/states, which greatly lowers the execution time of tests. Model-based testing also simplifies the process of reproducing discovered crashes and faults, as the tool can easily describe the sequence of actions and states that were used to reach the fault state. This method also improves instruction and code coverage, as it can more effectively trigger specific events in target states.

Tools like APE[7], EHBDroid[9], and Stoat[4] have become benchmarks in the model-based testing area. Stoat utilizes a finite state machine model to describe the behavior of the app. By weighing an event's type and frequency of execution, Stoat creates a priority list of events to execute. It then uses Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling to generate test cases for the model. EHBDroid optimizes

model-based algorithms by directly invoking the event-handlers, which allows the tool to access states that are harder to reach while purely invoking GUI widgets. APE starts with a general abstraction and dynamically optimizes its abstraction’s granularity by leveraging information gained during runtime.

2.3 Systematic testing

Systematic testing is a functional and comprehensive method of testing apps. It relies on the tester to understand the application behavior, create specific test cases to validate user workflows, and often requires instrumentation of the app’s software. The challenge with systematic testing arises in generating these inputs and situations, as they vary greatly from app to app and require manual effort.

Figure 1.3: Systematic testing workflow

These tools [10-14] use techniques such as symbolic execution to provide specific inputs for targeted application behavior. Symbolic execution partitions the domain of possible inputs and categorizes them into groups that correspond to a unique code path. These strategies are designed to traverse code paths that are harder to execute and reach using other strategies. These tools also reverse-engineer the APK to generate the required inputs to cover specific program paths.

The advantage of systematic testing is that it can achieve higher code coverage of the app under test as it lends for deeper exploration of possible code paths and states of the app. However, systematic testing is difficult to scale for apps with large code sizes due to the problem of path explosion. These approaches are also white-box in nature and require internal knowledge and instrumentation of the app’s software to achieve high code coverage. Another disadvantage of this approach is that the tests need to be frequently updated as the app software evolves or new security vulnerabilities are discovered.

One of the most prominent systematic automated testing tools to date is Sapienz[14]. Sapienz uses a Pareto-optimal multi-objective search-based approach [20], which uses methods like mutation to generate new test cases. However, these methods of test generation often lead to invalid sequences, causing a large time loss. TimeMachine [15] grows upon Sapienz by restarting the algorithm at previously explored states

that seem promising when the current search stagnates. TimeMachine uses state-level feedback to detect which promising screens have actions yet to be explored, allowing it to cover significantly more code.

2.4 Machine Learning-based testing

Machine learning (ML) is a programming technique that provides apps the ability to automatically learn and improve from experience without being explicitly programmed to do so. The self-learning capability makes ML-based testing well suited for testing a large variety of apps and for building blackbox testing tools that can dynamically learn the app characteristics. Regressive Learning (RL) is emerging as one of the main ML techniques in automated testing tools, as it trains by trial and error and is able to handle a wide variety of events. RL-based testing tools can be broadly classified into two main categories - a) explicit training tools and b) runtime training tools. The explicit training tools use a large number of apps to train a model that can learn about app characteristics and the relevance of various events. These tools leverage their *experience* from previous testing to train a model which can then be used to test new apps based on this trained model. QBE [16] uses a set of Android apps to determine the relative importance of various event types in optimizing code coverage or fault detection.

Similar approaches often have to create state abstractions in order to make it possible for knowledge to be transferred between applications. However, due to the flexible design of mobile apps, this knowledge can be useless while guiding the testing of the target application.

The second category of tools consists of those that model independently for every app or create general abstraction models. This category includes tools like QDroid[17] and Q-testing, which incorporate a reinforcement learning algorithm known as Q-learning. Many tools in this category, like QDroid, simply extend AutoBlackTest[18], another machine learning algorithm, so they do not have explicit training processes. The majority of tools in this category use Q-learning to guide their testing. Figure 1.4 below shows the workflow for a Q-learning runtime training ML tool.

Figure 1.4: Model-based testing workflow

State-of-the-art techniques that utilize machine learning typically use regressive learning to guide their tools. Q-testing[19] uses a delayed reward Q-learning system that rewards actions depending on the values of subsequent states from that actions. DeepGUI is a tool for detecting GUI events with higher accuracy by using heatmaps, and it has been prototyped into Monkey++, an extension of Monkey. ARES[20] is an algorithm framework that utilizes multiple different types of regressive learning, including DDPG[21], TD3[22], and SAC[23].

Despite the powers of machine learning, there are still several key obstacles that prevent ML tools from realizing their full potential. Due to the wide variety of Android apps, widgets, and GUI types, it is often difficult for tools to utilize knowledge gained from other applications in guiding testing of the target app. Furthermore, since Q-learning saves an entry for every state-action pair, memory soon becomes an issue, as the number of entries grows rapidly.

3. Research Methodology

In this section, we describe the methodology we used to evaluate the approaches to automated testing of mobile apps described in the *Literature review* section.

Assess: First, we conducted a detailed review of research publications in this area over the last ten years to build a comprehensive understanding of the various tools and approaches to automated testing and classified them into four broad categories mentioned in the Literature Review section. For each category, we then did another round of publication review to identify the most commonly used algorithms and tools that are considered state-of-the-art.

Acquire: Our initial plan was to acquire primary data to compare these tools by downloading the tools and running comparative tests for a suite of Android apps and comparing their performance. However, we realized that the tools themselves have varied levels of software maturity. They require different configurations, software versions, and platforms. Given these challenges, we modified our approach to using the primary data sources provided by the researchers to compare these tools. Specifically, we used the performance results published for comparison.

Analyze: The approach of using data sources provided by the publications came with its own challenges. Every researcher publishes data points that are interesting and useful to them, but papers are rarely published with the intent of comparative evaluation in relation to well-known benchmarks. To address these variations in primary data sources, we identified 3 quantitative metrics as the key metrics for comparative analysis of effectiveness of different approaches: code coverage, error detection, and test execution time. *Code coverage* is a measurement of how many lines of code are executed while the automated tests are running. *Error detection* is the ability to detect the presence of errors caused by bugs or other vulnerabilities. *Test execution time* is the time needed to achieve a certain code coverage.

Baseline: As described above, Android has the largest share of the current mobile market and is open-source. Google's Android Developer Studio provides a default testing tool called Monkey[2] which is widely used as an out-of-package baseline testing tool. We used the performance characteristics of Monkey as a baseline to compare and contrast the other tools. This enabled us to evaluate all these automated testing tools and compare their relative performances.

4. Results and Findings

4.1 Monkey

The current standard for automated Android testing lies with Google’s default testing tool, Monkey[2]. The Monkey is a command-line tool that generates pseudo-random UI events to transition from state to state. The tool’s main appeal lies in the fact that it is a *black-box algorithm*, making it easily implementable regardless of the application’s internal details. The tool’s random nature and consistency allow it to achieve high coverage, and it is widely used for black-box stress testing.

One of the Monkey’s biggest weaknesses, however, is its inability to leverage the information it gains during testing. It performs random events on any screen regardless of the knowledge it has acquired beforehand. Monkey also frequently generates events that have no impact on the app (like clicking on the background), as it is completely random. This makes the execution times longer than optimal. The random nature of the tool also makes reproducing test runs and issues almost impossible. Due to these inefficiencies in its algorithm, developers have begun to create tools to outperform Monkey in both code coverage and fault detection.

4.2 Sapienz

Sapienz[14] focuses on minimizing the length of test sequences while still achieving good coverage. It uses a white-box testing approach while providing various levels of instrumentation depending on the accessibility available for the tester. White-box testing refers to test cases based on the code itself, whereas black-box testing is done without the internal knowledge of the program.

At the lowest level, when the app’s source code is available, Sapienz uses detailed instrumentation at the statement level. If only the binary APK file is available, a more frequent automated testing scenario, Sapienz uses a mixed approach if repackaging is permitted. When repackaging is disallowed, like in most commercial apps, Sapienz takes a black-box approach, using activity-level coverage to guide its testing.

Across the 60 benchmark applications, Sapienz was able to cover 5% more instructions than Monkey, resulting in a **10.42%** performance increase over Monkey. It also covered a stunning 101 crashes to Monkey’s 39, a **159%** increase. Sapienz was able to find more crashes due to its focus on minimizing test sequence length, which allowed for higher efficiency during testing.

4.3 APE

APE[7] is a fully automated model-based tool for effective testing of Android apps. APE has a general, decision tree-based representation of state extraction functions in order to build a good testing model. It also has a novel evolution mechanism to dynamically and continuously update the model to achieve a good balance between model size and model precision.

Rather than create the model map of an application as it travels through different states, APE instead creates a default abstraction to initiate testing. While testing the application, it refines the model to make a more accurate abstraction. However, unlike most model-based testing algorithms, APE dynamically adjusts the level of abstraction detail based on the amount needed. APE determines this level through a decision tree, which is tuned on the fly with feedback obtained during testing. This results in a huge improvement in coverage, and it displays the power of APE. The dynamic nature of APE allows it to adapt to more complicated GUI trees and models. Its ability to develop GUI abstractions that discard irrelevant GUI details while accurately reflecting the states of the app under test makes it stand out from previous, more static algorithms.

APE's model-based approach together with dynamic adjustment of the model makes it a powerful tool for blackbox testing. In tests of 15 benchmark apps, APE consistently performed better than Monkey.

Across 15 benchmark apps, APE covered 3.6% more of the app's software in the same execution time as Monkey, or a **16.72%** improvement over Monkey. In terms of fault detection, APE was able to detect nearly **41%** more crashes than Monkey. In a few cases, Monkey was able to find more defects and cover more instructions than APE. Due to the tool's randomness, it managed to select events that seemed less promising to APE, allowing it to gain a higher coverage. However, the publication presenting APE only compared the two tools to 15 benchmark apps, which may not be sufficient for a thorough comparison to Monkey.

Note: Some apps show poor coverage performance from automated testing tools. This is not a limitation of the tools, as some of these apps require certain permissions to access a section of their code (for example, a premium account).

4.4 Deep GUI/Monkey++

A major obstacle that GUI-based automated testing faces is the accurate detection of GUI events. In recent years, creators of testing algorithms have turned to more intricate methods to maximize the probability of selecting touchable events. Malek et al. achieve this through Deep GUI [24], which uses deep learning to create a heatmap that gives pixels with a higher probability of being part of a widget a higher “heat”. Hotter pixels are more likely to be selected, and this allows Deep GUI to select valid events with higher probability. Deep GUI is not a tool itself but a method to generate test events with more accuracy. To determine its efficiency, the creators implemented a prototype of DeepGUI into a tool called Monkey++ by extending Google’s Monkey[2] tool.

Over all 30 benchmark applications, the performances of Monkey++ and Monkey were similar. Monkey++ only covered an additional **0.93%** of the app's code than Monkey, or a **1.82%** performance increase over Monkey. However, Monkey++ shines in apps with more complexity, as its main contribution is the ability to detect more complicated apps. In the ten benchmark apps with the highest crawling complexity, Monkey++ was able to cover **4.8%** more code than Monkey, with a **8.25%** increase in performance over Monkey. Monkey++ also covered instructions faster than Monkey, and it reached 50% line coverage in the ten apps with the highest complexity in 9 minutes, while Monkey required almost 20 minutes.

4.5 ARES

The state space of Android apps is massive, and the best exploration strategies are highly dependent on the specific features of the AUT. This means that it is very difficult to build a generic and static solution that is able to efficiently test all sorts of Android applications. However, in the past few years, a specific technique of machine learning known as reinforcement learning has displayed promise in testing a wide variety of apps. Reinforcement learning is a technique that learns the optimal strategy to solve a task with trial and error with a reward system. Some tools specifically use Deep RL, a fusion between reinforcement learning and neural networks. The capabilities of neural networks make Deep RL a viable technique for exploring complex spaces, like those of Android applications. ARES is one of the most recently developed tools that use a Deep RL approach for black-box testing of Android applications. It is essentially a plug-in framework for different RL algorithms, and it currently utilizes 5 different algorithms: DDPG[21], TD3[22], SAC[23], Q-learning, and Random. DDPG and TD3 are based on a deterministic policy gradient [25], which allows them to operate over continuous action spaces. On the

other hand, SAC is non-deterministic and focuses on entropy regularization. ARES’s motive to use these three new RL-based testing methods lies in Q-learning’s inability to handle larger action spaces. While Q-learning is able to handle a large observation space, it is limited to discrete and low-dimensional action spaces due to its tabular nature. ARES sidesteps this issue with DDPG and TD3, as they are better suited to handle high-dimensional action spaces with their continuous policy gradients. ARES is also purely black-box, as it only relies on the GUI of the application under test.

Over the 67 benchmark apps, ARES covered 10.2% more of the application code on average, or a **23.4%** increase in performance over Monkey. It was also able to detect 171 faults to Monkey’s 53, a **223%** increase. ARES showed a significant dominance in most applications, and it frequently covered 10% more code of an application than Monkey.

4.6 DeepGUIT

Q-learning is a specific technique in machine learning that has recently gained traction in the automated testing world. Q-learning is a reinforcement learning-based algorithm that tries to learn the “value” of a certain action in a given state. In an automated testing scenario, actions that lead to new and promising states earn a higher value, which is then fed into the Q-table. However, as each state-action pair is registered as a new entry, the number of entries that are stored in the Q-table grows rapidly, and memory becomes a significant issue. DeepGUIT[26] is a white-box testing algorithm that uses Q-learning to guide its testing. It instruments the app code and assigns higher rewards to state-action pairs using Bellman’s equation [27].

Over the 15 benchmark applications, DeepGUIT was able to cover 54% of app instructions on average, compared to Monkey’s 34%, giving it a **58.9%** increase in performance over Monkey. It was also able to detect 34 faults and crashes over Monkey’s 28, resulting in a **21.4%** increase in fault detection performance. DeepGUIT was able to consistently outperform Monkey in the given benchmark apps, but the two tools were only compared against 15 benchmark applications. To mitigate this threat of validity, the developers of DeepGUIT intentionally selected applications with different sizes and GUI widgets.

5. Conclusions

In the previous section, we did an in-depth side-by-side comparison of key quantitative metrics of 5 commonly used tools against a benchmark tool - Monkey. In this section, we summarize how these tools stack up against each other in terms of code coverage and their ability to detect faults. We also do a comparison of the qualitative aspects of these tools and then conclude on the recommendation for the tools that are most suited for testing various apps.

	Sapienz	APE	Monkey++	ARES	DeepGUIT
Code coverage improvement	10.4%	16.7%	8.3%	23.4%	58.8%
Fault detection improvement	159.0%	41.0%	-	223.0%	21.4%
Testing modes	Multi-mode	Black-box	Black-box	Black-box	White-box
Testing Approach	Systematic	Model	Random	ML	ML

Table 1: Results of the evaluation

Table 1 captures the relative performance for each of the 5 testing tools against Monkey. The ML-based tools and Systematic testing tools show significantly higher efficacy in detecting faults when compared to tools using random or model-based algorithms. This is an expected result for the random testing algorithms as they do not leverage information gained during runtime to build an understanding of the app, are completely non-deterministic in their actions, can be repetitive and not comprehensive in coverage. Model-based testing performs better in code coverage metrics but is unable to perform at the same fault detection level as ARES and Sapienz. The state abstraction model used by APE allows it to recognize which states are promising and guides the tool to unexplored locations. This boosts the tool’s code coverage.

Sapienz displayed impressive fault detection capability with an improvement of 159% over Monkey. However, these results do not fully capture Sapienz’s true potential. The data provided in the publication introducing Sapienz [14] details its performance in black-box mode. It is even more effective in white-box mode, which requires instrumentation of the application code. Systematic testing is a promising method for white-box testing of an app, as it is able to cover large amounts of code and is specialized in finding faults and crashes. More tools, such as TimeMachine[cite from above], are building off of Sapienz and introducing new systematic tactics to improve the efficiency of systematic testing.

ARES and DeepGUIT display the power of Machine learning and its potential in the creation of intelligent automated testing tools. ARES's capability to handle a wide variety of inputs and activities allowed it to find over 3 times as many faults as Monkey. DeepGUIT's Q-learning algorithm and neural network allow it to learn about the app internals and discover paths and states with higher potential more frequently, resulting in a 50% performance increase in code coverage over Monkey.

There are other factors that drive the adoption of testing frameworks as well. Tools that can shorten test execution time while not compromising on fault detection and code coverage are more likely to be adopted by app developers. While Monkey++[24] did not show a significant increase in code coverage over Monkey, it was twice as fast while exploring algorithms, taking around 10 minutes on average to reach 50% coverage, compared to Monkey's 20 minutes. Monkey++'s speed increase can be attributed to its focus on improving event detection accuracy. By avoiding redundancies and focusing on promising events, the tool was able to optimize its paths through the application and cover more of an application in a shorter time.

Another factor that is important for tool adoption is the ease of use and the time it takes to develop tests. A white-box testing and systematic testing tools like Sapeinz require upfront work from app developers to create detailed workflows and tests. They also require developers to instrument their code to gain high levels of code coverage. For smaller companies and app developers, this can be a source of friction for adopting these techniques.

Machine learning based techniques have the potential to significantly improve both code coverage (+58.8%) as well as fault detection (+223%). Their ability to expand coverage and optimize execution time by *learning* from prior executions gives them a significant advantage over methods. Lastly, ML-based testing tools are well suited for black-box testing and do not put the burden of instrumentation of code or test design on the app developers.

To summarize, while systematic testing is a good option for large companies that has the resources for the upfront work to maximize the fault detection, ML-based tools are a more promising and practical option for the large number of smaller sized app development companies.

6. Implications and Gaps

There are many approaches to automated testing and new tools are being developed around them. However, the current state-of-the-art automated testing solutions fall short of the requirements for applications with complex workflows and states. The code coverage metrics are on the lower side in absolute terms for most of the approaches. The fault detection ability also varies significantly across different apps, and when coupled with low code coverage, many faults and crashes still remain undetected. On the other hand, AI and machine learning approaches promise to fundamentally change the landscape of automated mobile testing. As their methods of training and finding optimal paths improve, they can reach and surpass both manual and random testing. However, there are some key obstacles they need to overcome in order to realize their full potential. First, training algorithms need a large set of applications to train the model but the apps as well as Android are constantly evolving with new features, attributes and event types. Second, current training algorithms do not fully utilize the knowledge gained from testing previous apps when exploring the target application due to the wide variety of Android event types and sizes. Furthermore, the Q-learning technique that most state-of-the-art ML testing tools use faces memory issues when used on apps with large state spaces. Each state-action pair has a separate entry in the algorithm's Q-table, so the memory required increases combinatorially, limiting the tool's

applicability. When ML tools are able to sidestep these limitations, they will be able to cover larger amounts of code and detect more faults and crashes.

7. Future Work - A Hybrid Approach

In this section, we propose a novel approach to Android app testing that combines the advantages of model-based testing approach with computer vision and RL-based exploration techniques to significantly improve code coverage metrics for a broad spectrum of Android apps. To motivate the new approach, we share a set of core requirements for the new tool.

7.1 Requirements

For a test tool to effectively test real-world Android applications, it needs to satisfy the following core requirements:

Robust: The tool should be able to handle complex Android applications with large state spaces.

Black-box: The tool should forgo the need for instrumenting the app's code and the ability to decompile the app's binaries.

Versatile: The tool must be capable of effectively testing a broad spectrum of Android apps ranging from simple apps to large apps with complex activities and app functionalities.

Automated: The tool should minimize necessary manual effort.

Efficient: The tool should avoid generating redundant inputs and aim to cover more instructions when possible in a deterministic way.

7.2 Hybrid Approach

The proposed approach splits the testing of the app in two distinct parts. The first part will use computer vision to extract common events and actions from the app. The extraction is done across a large number of apps and across many widgets within each app. The resulting data set of events is then used to train a Q-learning-like neural network and creates a mapping of widgets and actions to events that is optimized to maximize app exploration. This part of the algorithm is completely black-box and will require no instrumentation from the app developers. In fact, this part is also platform agnostic and can be easily extended beyond Android to iOS apps as well.

The second part of the algorithm is similar to existing model-based approaches. The 3 key steps are - a) Taking the screenshot of the app screen, b) using computer vision to detect widget attributes and events and c) using the trained model from part 1 to select events for execution. Figure R1 below shows the workflow of the hybrid approach.

Figure R1: Current Workflow of our Tool

7.3 Proposed Algorithm

As stated, the hybrid algorithm uses two phases and alternates between learning about the app through discovery and intelligent events selection to optimize exploitation of the code path. The algorithm starts with an empty GUI model and begins by randomly selecting events at new screens it encounters. During this exploration phase (Phase 1), the tool will randomly select an action on the current screen, analyze the new screen, and store the resulting (s, a, s') ¹ tuple, creating an edge-based graph model. The tool analyzes the new screen by taking a screenshot and using the computer vision library *cv2*[28] to detect bounding boxes in the image. These bounding boxes represent the potential user events (like touch) on the screen for the algorithm to explore. The algorithm stores a list of these events at each new screen. When the tool activates Phase 2, it targets a nearby state based on the trained model that has not been fully explored. It then uses a breadth-first search algorithm to redirect the tool towards the state. When encountered with a new state, the algorithm falls back to Phase 1 and continues exploring from the target state. This approach can help maximize code coverage by traversing to states that have not been *explored* in-depth while also enhancing fault detection by in depth testing of discovered states by using the trained neural network to fully *exploit* states that have some level of coverage already. Figure R2 displays the pseudocode of the algorithm.

¹ s represents the current state, a represents the executed action, and s' represents the result state.

```

1)  $V = []$ 
2) Loop
  a) take screenshot  $S$ 
  b) if not there exists a screenshot  $S'$  in  $V$ , such that
     similar( $S, S'$ )
     i) compute list of available events  $L_s$  from  $S$ 
     ii) let  $A_s = L_s$ 
     iii) let  $e =$  random event from  $A_s$ .
     iv) remove  $e$  from  $A_s$ 
     v) execute  $e$ 
     vi) add  $S$  to  $V$ 
  c) else
     i) if  $A_s$  is non-empty
        (1) let  $e =$  random event from  $A_s$ 
        (2) remove  $e$  from  $A_s$ 
        (3) execute  $e$ 
     ii) else
        (1) use BFS, find nearest screen with unexplored
            events
        (2) travel to this screen and continue

```

Figure R2: Pseudocode of the algorithm

7.4 Next Steps

Currently, the algorithm is implemented as a new testing tool in Python and uses the cv2 library for detecting events on the screen using computer vision algorithms. The initial implementation of the tool can successfully detect events and widgets across a variety of apps using cv2, build a state machine model for the app and select events to explore the app under test. The tool is still under development and uses the default event selection to randomly select events to execute on a screen to progress through the application. We plan to incorporate regressive learning to improve the tool's method of event selection. The ML algorithm will focus on selecting types of events that have led to promising events while avoiding events that were redundant on previous screens. This will increase our algorithm's code coverage and efficiency, as the algorithm will select events that are more likely to lead to a new state and fewer redundant events will be executed. The tool also needs to be tested on a large number of apps for its efficacy and benchmarking against Monkey and other existing tools.

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